

Lessons Learned: A Smartphone App for Information Behaviour Research

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Abstract

This article provides insights and lessons learned from developing and using a smartphone application (app) for information behaviour research. In our third-party-funded project on health information behaviour in Germany, a custom app served as a tailored research tool, offering comprehensive process control and enabling contextual data collection. Custom-built apps can address specific challenges in qualitative research while providing advantages like improved data collection efficiency and real-time monitoring. However, unlike commercial apps, developing a research-specific app involves unique goals, challenges, and requirements. We found this to be a complex task demanding expertise, time, and flexibility. Providing researchers with access to reflective literature is crucial for making the most of these tools. This article contributes to that body of work by sharing our experiences and lessons learned. We address challenges and solutions from our project, supported by examples and recommendations from the literature, covering areas such as requirements engineering, budgeting, data privacy, testing, and operations management.

Keywords: research method; research tool; smartphone application; information behaviour; health information; lessons learned

1 Introduction

This article provides insights and lessons learned on developing and utilising a smartphone application in information behaviour research, in particular, for

DESIVE², a third-party-funded project on health information behaviour in Germany.¹ In the project, we collected long-term data using a self-developed smartphone application (app). The app (Fig. 1) allowed participants to upload screenshots, voicemails, or documents accompanied by supplementary information (i.e., answers to predefined questions) and to answer surveys.

Fig. 1 Screenshots of the self-developed app in German, depicting the home screen, the voice recording feature, and a survey page with additional questions to be answered.

An app specifically developed for one’s research need can be a valuable tool for addressing specific challenges found in qualitative research (Do & Yamagata-Lynch, 2017; Frąckowiak et al., 2023) as well as for enhancing “the qualitative research process for both researchers and participants” (Welford et al., 2022, p. 194). Undeniably, utilising such an app for research brings numerous advantages, including enhanced data collection efficiency and opportunities for real-time monitoring. It is possible, among other things, to collect various types of data, including text, audio, images, and video, and it provides researchers with an entry point into the complex experiences and insights of participants while working in situ (Johnson, 2013). It is an important aspect also highlighted by Lathia (2022, p. 22): “As smart mobile phones permeate society, so too does the opportunity to use these technolo-

1 <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/desive2>

gies to unobtrusively capture patterns of daily life and interact with people in situ”. Although self-developing an app allows for better tailoring to the project’s research questions and for controlling the process comprehensively while collecting contextual research data, app development comes with unique goals, challenges, and considerations – not only of technical nature. This is especially the case when researchers from different disciplines and with different degrees of experience in software development come together for such an endeavour for the first time. Similar to Frąckowiak et al. (2023, p. 1379), we experienced that “developing, testing, and improving [an app for research] involved more complicated procedures than we initially thought”. Frąckowiak and his colleagues attribute their challenges to the “romantic myth” – the “belief that technology will miraculously solve (some of) the key difficulties and complexities of qualitative social research” (p. 1380). We learned that developing an app for research is a complex task that requires expertise, time, and flexibility. “It is therefore essential that researchers, when considering adopting such tools, are able to draw on a body of literature that includes reflections and learning on the process to maximise benefits” (Welford et al., 2022, p. 193). We aim to offer these kinds of reflections as well as our lessons learned, supplemented by scientific literature on smartphone apps as a research tool.

Using an app for information behaviour research can significantly improve the process of participation (Frąckowiak et al., 2023). It enables participants to upload content or answer questions directly from their smartphones or other mobile devices, whenever they discover content relevant for the study while still using the same device. This approach circumvents the issue of ‘media disruption’, which refers to interruptions or inconsistencies in the transfer of information across various media or communication channels (Keusch et al., 2019). Brandt et al. (2007) showed that entries were more likely to be submitted both easily and consistently when the same device was employed for both observing and reporting. A well-designed app is easy to use and appealing, offers flexibility, and can collect data in real-time (Welford et al., 2022). It enables researchers to explore “real-life patterns” (Hektner et al., 2007, as cited in Seifert et al., 2018) and conduct “naturalistic observation” (Frąckowiak et al., 2023, p. 1380) of information behaviour – even remotely. Additionally, the sensors built into mobile devices provide the possibility of gathering “passive data” as well, supplementing self-reports for more contextual information (Seifert et al., 2018, p. 2; Wenz & Keusch, 2023).

The DESIVE²-project deals with the understanding of health information behaviour, considering the surge in mis- and disinformation, as for example, during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our research approach was based on grounded theory, involving iterative long-term data collection through user-supplied content, interviews, and surveys. Thus, our methodology prioritised a flexible approach consisting of individual interactions with participants, utilising a dedicated mobile application to collect qualitative data to understand (dis)information behaviour in health contexts comprehensively. Due to the iterative nature of our research and the desire for a tailored solution to accommodate the specific requirements of our study, we made the strategic decision to develop the app internally and not have it developed by an external agency. This way, we were able to create a research tool that would meet all our methodological needs (Do & Yamagata-Lynch, 2017).

Now, after we have discussed and motivated the use of (self-developed) apps in qualitative research, we will, in the following sections, describe challenges and solutions experienced and found within our project, supplemented by examples and recommendations from the literature. In section 2, we divided the development cycle into five categories: Planning, Conceptualisation, App Design & Content, Implementation, and Evaluation & Feedback. Section 3 covers data privacy, security and management. We briefly talk about team communication in section 4 before we conclude our lessons learned in section 5. The significance of these “lessons learned” lies in their potential to inform and guide future endeavours in the intersection of information behaviour research and app development. We hope these insights provide valuable findings for researchers, developers, and practitioners seeking to navigate the complex landscape of developing apps to conduct research.

2 Developing an App for Research

2.1 Planning

A major difference between app development for commercial versus research projects lies in prioritizing the research objective as the primary consideration for each step, instead of a commercial goal. In a research project, decisions are made differently, with varying emphasis on different factors influ-

encing those decisions (e.g., methodological particularities, different restrictions on time and money, GDPR compliance and ethical responsibilities, priority on building trust and reducing bias vs. profit). This results in a different method of approach when defining the main goals of a project, as a clear path might not be predestined, especially in qualitative research, and the focus of the research can change significantly based on new findings. However, a clear and early definition of research goals and the requirements, budgets, and time spans are essential for most research projects, for example to secure funding. This field of tension highlights that both researchers and developers must be involved as early and as intensively as possible in the development process to successfully tap their knowledge and evaluation skills and reduce complications later on (e.g., time delay, higher cost, necessity of re-coordination of tasks). It is also important to consider that the planned study design and data collection techniques may pose challenges for the design and development of an app, especially if innovative ideas or new concepts are to be incorporated. For this reason, it is advisable to carefully consider alternatives and their advantages and disadvantages, for example, if existing (commercial) services can be used and if they are feasible from a data protection and data security point of view.

Another relevant point, centering around the proactive consideration and planning of research budgets, are the costs associated with technical infrastructure. In our project, it became evident that, at the outset of a research endeavour, obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the expenses linked to the required technical components is paramount. Notably, unforeseen costs may arise during and after the planning phase, surpassing initial estimations. Thus, expenses might include not only the acquisition of essential hardware but also the required memberships for software platforms, which were not initially considered. For example, Apple demands an annual fee for the publication of apps on their app store. Additionally, the research budget must include licensing fees for website tools, server costs, domain registrations, and other easily overlooked expenditures. These examples underscore the necessity of involving experienced developers and domain experts in the project planning or, more specifically, in drafting the project proposal that lays the foundations for app development. Siegler et al. (2021, p. 6) recommend the “inclusion of an independent and research-versed developer to the research team” to avoid the “problem of information asymmetry” and “minimize potential problems regarding the scope of work and oversight of project development”.

Lastly, consideration of technological alternatives should also be part of the planning process. Is an app truly necessary? Evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of various technological solutions is essential to ensure optimal alignment with research goals. Corresponding research demonstrates that leveraging existing channels (e.g., WhatsApp) can be advisable because participants are “already using the app daily, easy-to-use voice messaging and content sharing features, as well as the availability of a desktop/web application that allows the researchers to use text templates and more comfortably organise the communication with participants” (Kümpel, 2022, p. 192). For future research projects, we recommend comparing alternatives and to not stay set on a certain tool or technology. For example, a useful alternative could be to develop a chatbot instead of a mobile app. It could possibly be a more efficient way to collect data from participants because the availability of commonly used messaging apps makes it easier to send notifications, use text templates, and organise the communication with participants (Kaufmann & Peil, 2020).

2.2 Conceptualisation

The start of every software development project is the collection and definition of requirements, which are necessarily subjective to the goals of the (research) project and the tasks the software should fulfil. Hence, we illustrate general considerations for conceptualising software by taking DESIVE²-goals as examples. To achieve our research goal, we decided on the following general conditions: The project consists of a two-staged exploratory study over a period of approximately six months each. The study process involves obtaining content relevant to the research topic (e.g., screenshots of conversations, feeds, or news outlets covering health topics) in the form of regularly self-reported media artifacts and surveys (e.g., demographic questions and questions regarding individual health information behaviour) from the participants through a smartphone app (in addition to conducting independent qualitative interviews). The participants were individuals who had previously seen or spread potential scientific (mis)information through social media or other channels and volunteered to participate in our research.

We took several steps to support high engagement and ease of participation for our study participants. Participants could upload content, via their own devices, at any time during their participation, which in our project context was about ten weeks. Participation was motivated through staggered

monetary incentives, regular emails, and push notifications on the users' devices.

In our study, an effective administration of the study and study participants on the backend side required the implementation of a user-friendly interface tailored for the seamless modification of user accounts and efficient management of incentives. As requested by our research team, the interface allowed administrators to make necessary adjustments to user profiles while also handling incentive management during and after the study. A user-interface for the database simplifies these administrative tasks and contributes to a more efficient and responsive participant management system.

In addition to the requirements specified by the study design, external factors had to be considered as well. These included privacy regulation compliance, data and system sovereignty, and the flexibility of data formats for analysis and long-term storage, which will be discussed in section 3, "Data Management & Privacy".

2.3 App design and content

The interplay between a research study design and app development is a dynamic challenge with bidirectional influences. The specifics of the research design may impose constraints on app functionalities while simultaneously, the capabilities of the app affect the research itself. It prompts a critical examination of what is technically feasible and sensible. An example of this aspect is the implementation of frontend requirements: appealing designs, smooth animations, and high-performance servers are the standard when using everyday apps. When developing an app within a research project, one may come to the conclusion that those aspects are desired but only as a second priority. Finite development time and resources, as well as a limited number of developers, may result in the majority of programming being dedicated to ensuring the essential functions, not more. Further planned designs, animations, or functionalities may have to either be implemented later or even be scrapped. Considering the aforementioned points, transparent team communication and early clarification that such a scientific app may not meet the aesthetical and technological standards of global players must be guaranteed. However, it was reported that a plain design may even further participants' trust in a research app, as it is clearly distinguishable from commercial apps (Frąckowiak et al., 2023).

On another note, it is critical to recognise that an app is more than a mere compilation of functions related to the central goal of a study, as, for instance, the possibility of answering questionnaires as an isolated feature. In comparison to an online questionnaire, the utilization of an app necessitates the creation of additional content, leading users through the app. This includes, among others, descriptions, instructional texts, error messages, or texts for push notifications. The integration of textual and visual elements, coupled with the necessity for effective support communication, significantly increases the workload and coordination efforts required to create a unified participant experience. This aspect is not to be underestimated in the initial planning stages, and researchers undertaking app development projects should ensure clarity regarding the responsibility for content creation, user support, and others, which is essential to avoid potential challenges and inconsistencies in messaging leading to confused participants, diminished engagement, and potential miscommunication of study objectives. The creation of textual and visual content independently of technical development, however, could be problematic, as the technical feasibility of design and workflow decisions needs to be taken into account.

2.4 Implementation

When estimating the effort required to develop and maintain the necessary technical architecture for the app, one must consider several aspects. First and foremost, we learned that bug-free software is an unlikely goal to achieve, with some authors arguing that it is unattainable (Glass, 2003; Frąckowiak et al., 2023). One of many examples from our project is the regular occurrence of software updates containing fixes for specific malfunctions, sometimes resulting in the emergence of new bugs. These include not only “app failures” but also “device failures” (Barriage & Hicks, 2020, pp. 5–9; Frąckowiak et al., 2023). While others highlight the progress made in identifying bugs through extensive software testing (Khan et al., 2020; Menendez, 2021), we have to conclude that software testing is a process that can never be seen as complete until the apps’ use as a research tool ends.

This may sound more fatalistic than it is, nevertheless, it tends to have a realistic effect on the team’s expectations and morale (see also Frąckowiak, 2023). We would therefore like to stress the critical need for a pragmatic and proactive approach to calculate the required development efforts and address issues over the whole software lifecycle. Development includes testing- and

bug-reporting processes, as well as determining responsibilities and tools to manage these. Screen capture recordings (videos) with commentary proved to be a useful and user-friendly solution to report bugs efficiently, and we recommend including this feature in the reporting process.

The selection of a robust platform framework reduces the work required for the implementation of standard functionalities. In our project, we used Xamarin² but since it is no longer supported, an alternative is .NET MAUI³ for building cross-platform mobile apps. Using such a framework also helped to determine the operating systems and versions supported, which was paramount to limit complexity for us.

An important aspect in this regard is the (first) digital divide, which means that technology should be equally accessible. However, in reality, there is an economic gap, which hinders, for example, poorer participants from taking part because, for instance, new software is only compatible with expensive new hardware and the latest models of smartphones (Sung, 2016). In our implementation, we ensured a high level of backward compatibility, which resulted in the support of at least Android 6.0 (API Level 23, “Marshmallow”) and iOS 10 on Apple devices. Looking at current statistics, we estimated to be able to include more than 95% of smartphones in use this way (Apple, 2024; StatCounter, 2024a, 2024b).

In addition, a source code management system should be used to keep track of the development process and also the issues found, as well as automate the deployment process for testing and production environments. Depending on the study size, the scalability, and flexibility of the backend receiving and processing the data may play an important role to cater for increasing or fluctuating demand. Using technologies like containers and virtual machines can help implement a level of flexibility that is also beneficial with regard to moving to a new hosting infrastructure, as they then reduce the amount of work required for configuring the server software.

All of this may sound like a lot to consider; however, programming an app by yourself also has the significant advantage of having full control over almost all aspects. Two examples are being largely independent of third parties, and ensuring tailored and flexible solutions for software functionality.

2 <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/xamarin>

3 <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/maui>

2.5 Evaluation and feedback

The novelty, design, and usability of an app can directly influence the number of participants and their overall participation behaviour (Welford et al., 2022) and, therefore, influence the success of the research project. Roberts et al. (2022) report on advantages of using apps, such as a lower response burden or lower drop-out rates, and a positive influence concerning the willingness to continue participating in the study due to easier access. A user-oriented perspective should always be taken into account during development and as early as possible. While striking a balance between an innovative and reliable or easy-to-use interface, it helps to incorporate external expertise (e.g., gathered through focus groups or usability testing). Incorporating feedback in this way can also help to understand what motivates participants to engage and interact with the app. In our project, usability testing resulted in valuable feedback for both researchers and developers, which enabled us to improve the app's design, as well as add features to the app to improve the overall participant experience before the start of the study.

Another useful way to analyse the participants' behaviour within the app can be the broad collection of metrics data during the study (e.g., click data, time on specific pages, geolocation, browser history). While this could help understand how study participants are interacting with the app to optimise or evaluate it, it may not be what participants want to be sharing, which is relevant as informed consent is always needed (Keusch et al., 2019). The following section will go into more detail. Nevertheless, in every project, the usefulness of additional data and the necessity of it should (or in Europe must) be weighed against each other, following the European Union regulation for General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principle of data minimization (Art. 5 (1) c in GDPR (2016)).

In hindsight, we regret not having established more ways of evaluating our app, for example, with user surveys or even a survey among the research team. Still, the baseline is to provide easily accessible communication channels for feedback and technical support by the users. These could even be supplemented by training sessions and/or additional training materials for participants (Welford et al., 2022). Additionally, observing drop-out points and rates can help to identify and resolve usage barriers or broken functionality.

3 Data Management and Privacy

3.1 Data privacy and ethical considerations

The handling of data within a research project is characterised by two points of view, which are interdependent: compliance with legal requirements and forward-looking planning of short-, medium-, and long-term usage scenarios. Recognizing that research data is a valuable asset requiring particular attention and protection, one should respect the necessity of implementing the required legal framework (e.g., for the European Union the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016)) and conducting the necessary security measures throughout the entire data lifecycle. Laying out a plan for the specific usage of the data helps in doing this. With data privacy being a critical consideration in software development as well as information behaviour research, and developers playing a key role in addressing privacy requirements, the self-development of a research app ensured the opportunity for us to tailor the app for our requirements (Baldassarre et al., 2020) and adhere to GDPR (GDPR, 2016; Davidson et al., 2024). Here, it is crucial to mention that conducting research via an app requires significantly more attention to privacy and protection compared to online surveys or even filling out surveys on physical paper as digital data is also more prone to copying, distribution, or other potential risks.

While the use of, for example, informed consent forms for participants and ethical approvals for the project might be more common today (Asplund & Hulter Åsberg, 2021, p. 3), the comprehensive compliance with data protection laws and related responsibilities can pose some challenges for researchers not familiar with them. Furthermore, it is important to take into consideration that the legal use of data does not necessarily imply it being ethical. While the collection of detailed device information and the capture of all in-app interactions without transparent consent for purposes beyond the participant's reasonable expectations might prove valuable for economic considerations, this could be considered unethical as it violates the participant's trust, infringes on privacy expectations, and exploits personal information for purposes not originally communicated to the participant.

In general, the planned use of the acquired data for research purposes and, if applicable, beyond this (in the case of a full repository publication, i.e., source code as well as all research data), heavily influences the content of legal documents to be created. For example, the use (and publication) of non-

anonymized, user-generated data requires specific user consent and anonymization processes (GDPR, 2016), so we had to create specific privacy policies for the participants to accept as a requirement to participate in our study. Sharing the data collected via app among project partners of different legal entities required a legal framework for us as well (GDPR, 2016, Art. 26), which demands the cooperation of many administrative and legal parties and ample time for discussion. The same goes for the documentation of appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, as required by Article 32 of the GDPR. This is why we consider it highly advisable to incorporate data privacy and protection aspects early in the planning and development process and to use in-house consulting resources, if available. This can prevent delays caused by regulatory requirements and reduce the amount of work required to ensure a legally valid procedure.

3.2 Data security and cyberattacks

Participants do “have significant concerns about privacy control and information leakage” (Fung et al., 2022, p. 1) and are concerned when changes to privacy policies happen, as well as about their vulnerability to hacking and scamming (Frąckowiak et al., 2023; Maseeh et al., 2023). Neglecting this aspect can severely harm the research agenda if any data leakage incident is caused by missing security measures or documentation. This can be especially true for cases where GDPR-compliant deletion processes have not been implemented, and data that should not be stored and processed any more is being lost to attackers.

In addition to purely legal factors, it is also necessary to ensure a compliant technical implementation, taking into account, among other things, the three information security goals or principles laid out by Tamrin et al. (2017, pp. 145–146):

- “Confidentiality”, is defined “as the ability to ensure that information is accessible only to those with access authorization”,
- “Integrity”, is characterised as information only being modifiable by authorised parties, and
- “Availability”, described as the information being accessible and usable when needed.

Implementing these goals sometimes proved to be challenging, and different options needed to be carefully assessed. The confidentiality required, for

example, the implementation of authorization mechanisms when identifying participants/other users after weighing the (dis)advantages of various authentication mechanisms (Papathanasaki et al., 2022; Velásquez et al., 2018). Considering the availability, the implementation of automatic backup processes (i.e., the 3-2-1 backup strategy; Lobur et al., 2020) acts as a necessary proactive measure against potential data loss or system failures, which must be taken into consideration due to the everlasting threat of attacks on infrastructure. As part of that, a comprehensive plan for recovery needs to be established, outlining the steps to be taken in the case of a system failure or data corruption to ensure a rapid disaster recovery (Snedaker & Rima, 2014).

As unlikely as a complete failure of the infrastructure may seem in general, during the project we experienced a cyberattack on our research institute, which led to a complete shutdown of the IT infrastructure provided, severely limiting the availability of backend- and storage servers for months and leading even to the deletion of backups as a security measure. This posed important questions: How do we contact participants to inform them about a potential data leak when contact data is unavailable? How, when, and where can the infrastructure be rebuilt? In this case, the access to recent exports and backups containing the contact information of participants and the content uploaded by them, stored independently of the affected infrastructure, can be of great use. This allows for quickly rebuilding the backend infrastructure and keeping participants up-to-date about the developments in an emergency. However, building a parallel IT infrastructure needs additional resources, which has to be considered by funders. To summarise the aspects mentioned in this section, questions like the following need to be considered:

1. Where to host our infrastructure under consideration of data privacy and availability aspects?
2. Who is responsible for backups (and restoration), communication, and other associated tasks?
3. Which level of security measures are adequate and justifiable in the context of a research project?
4. What degree of communication regarding these topics is both essential and judicious for the participants?

In our case, no personal data was leaked. However, we still had to explain to participants why the survey was interrupted and used additional resources and time to rebuild our infrastructure.

3.3 Data management

Data management is important for requirements engineering and development of the app, but also for researchers who want to share their research data afterwards. Considering the use and reuse of collected participant data as early as possible aids the preparation of legal documents, as well as determining the scope of the data to be collected. Collecting additional data (e.g., usage and device information) to further evaluate the app, processes used, and outputs generated, should be considered, too. However, time and resource constraints after the planning phase can complicate a subsequent implementation. Atherly et al. (2021, p. 71) point out that data management plans should be documented, especially when designing studies utilising smartphones as a research tool. We realised this by creating and updating a versioned data management plan, documenting the materials, documents, source code and data use and created, as well as their format, license, location and, if applicable, deletion deadline or repository/archive destination.

Considering Open Science principles (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018), we advise creating a detailed data management plan for the sustained reusability of the developed software as well as the accumulated data after the end of the project. The public availability of research data after the end of a research project is, in our eyes, a desirable objective. This, however, requires heightened attention to ensure compliance with consent given by participants. It may also involve ensuring long-term maintenance and prioritizing transparent documentation. This approach is not only furthering the sustainability and reusability of our app, but also possibly increasing its impact and relevance in subsequent research.

4 The People Behind the App

Another vital aspect of app development is that a research team may involve people from different backgrounds or disciplines, who enrich the project with a diverse set of skills and perspectives but also potentially increase the need for additional support and communication in general. For example, some researchers may lack a comprehensive understanding of the process of programming an app, leading to difficult-to-achieve expectations regarding bug fixes and development timelines, or may need help in articulating and trans-

lating research requirements into actionable programming tasks (Siegler et al., 2021). Concerning these aspects, there is a need to define a shared knowledge level for internal (technical) communication.

To further streamline communication and understanding, it is advisable to conduct knowledge-sharing sessions to support team members in understanding the basics of each other's domains. This benefits not only the developers who gain a better understanding of the research methods but also every non-developer because of broader development insights. These insights are beneficial for swift conflict resolution, ensuring everyone involved can quickly address issues that may arise, while fostering a collaborative environment where team members can contribute more effectively to the project goals. Cultivating this knowledge foundation facilitates smoother communication, accelerates conflict resolution, and contributes to the project's success.

Another key takeaway from the development process was, understanding the effectiveness of visualisation tools for internal communication and requirement clarification. Merino et al. (2018) underscored the significance of these tools in offering an overview of the software development process, aiding teams in identifying potential issues and tracking process characteristics. The importance of concise communication regarding the app's visual and (simplified) functional aspects prompted the adoption of visualisation tools, such as Penpot⁴, allowing the generation of previews of pages within an app and the functional contexts as a crucial strategy. These tools can play a pivotal role in translating abstract ideas into tangible visual representations, fostering a shared understanding among team members. By leveraging visualisation tools, we aimed to clarify design expectations and facilitate collaborative decision-making within the research endeavour.

In summary, we want to outline that success lies most significantly in effective communication. From the clarity in defining research objectives to the thorough planning of development processes, communication has been the quintessence, and it becomes increasingly apparent that fostering a culture of transparent and proactive communication is not merely a consideration but an indispensable necessity.

4 <https://penpot.app/>

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the journey of developing an app for a health information behaviour research project has been enlightening. We learned where coding and research work well together and where synergies can still be improved. Leveraging this technology for data collection has led us to both opportunities and challenges, and we share the experiences Frąckowiak et al. (2023, p. 1384) described: “Facing all these—to some extent unexpected—difficulties, even our research team experienced a general exhaustion after several attempts to improve the software [...]. Paradoxically, this increased our [...] desire to look more closely at the application process itself”.

The quote highlights two important observations in the landscape of app development for research purposes. Firstly, encountering challenges of this nature is not uncommon, given the complex dynamics of such undertakings. Secondly, it emphasises the need for more honest reports on the scientific development of software. Indeed, while smartphones have become increasingly relevant in our day-to-day lives, “the potential for this to enhance the research process, particularly for qualitative research, is still an under-represented area of methodological literature” (Welford et al., 2022, p. 193). The publication of more comprehensive research in this field is not only warranted, but also essential for advancing the capabilities and understanding of software development in the context of research projects (Felderer et al., 2023). Reflecting on our experiences, we acknowledge the intricate nature of developing an app for research purposes, having experienced that the process involves more complexities than initially anticipated. Despite the challenges, our self-developed app allowed us to collect a rich and diverse sample of data to be analysed.

Throughout the development, we uncovered lessons that extended beyond mere descriptions of technical functionalities. Effective communication between project members emerged as one of the key points for success, from defining research objectives to planning development processes. Although enriching, collaboration between researchers and developers demands a shared knowledge level, emphasizing the importance of mutual understanding. With regard to the app development process, design considerations play a crucial role. Balancing study design constraints with possible app functionalities and programming effort associated requires a keen eye, particularly when resource limitations affect the realisation of certain features of both

research and app development. Another, not to be neglected, part of any consideration is the information provided within an app and through communication with the participants, which requires clear responsibilities within a team.

Because implementing bug-free software is hardly possible, focusing on realistic expectations and implementing processes for accepting feedback and issue reports is critical. Utilising existing software frameworks and adopting a comprehensive source code management system are pivotal decisions to reduce the effort required for the app development and help structuring the process. Testing and feedback processes will typically prove more complex than anticipated, emphasising the need to balance complexity, innovative features, and resources available while still ensuring usability through, for instance, focus groups and usability tests.

Other challenging tasks are not unique but are relevant in our research context, like ethical considerations, compliance with legal and privacy requirements, and thoughtful planning for data usage scenarios. Recognising the dual perspective of compliance with legal requirements and forward-looking planning, we advocate seeking expert help with adhering to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016) and other relevant legal frameworks. The handling of research data, viewed as a valuable asset requiring protection, necessitates a comprehensive approach. Implementing robust measures ensures data confidentiality, integrity, and availability, acknowledging the importance of safeguarding information against unauthorised access and modification. While often neglected, it is crucial to enhance the impact, relevance, and ethical standing in the broader academic landscape. A holistic approach, considering technical, design, and communication aspects, not only streamlines the development process but also significantly enhances the quality and effectiveness of the final research app as well as the whole research project.

As we move forward, sharing the lessons learned from our project, we aim to add our voice to the discourse between researchers, developers, and practitioners with the goal of crafting impactful, ethical, legal, and resilient apps for research purposes.

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References

- Apple (2024). IOS and iPadOS usage (2024, Jan. 12). <https://developer.apple.com/support/app-store/#nh>
- Asplund, K., & Hulter Åsberg, K. (2021). Reporting ethical approval in health and social science articles: An audit of adherence to GDPR and national legislation. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 22(1), 92. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-021-00664-w>
- Atherley, A., Hu, W., Teunissen, P. W., Hegazi, I., & Dolmans, D. (2021). Appraising the use of smartphones and apps when conducting qualitative medical education research: AMEE Guide No. 130. *Medical Teacher*, 43(1), 68–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2020.1838461>
- Baldassarre, M. T., Barletta, V. S., Caivano, D., & Piccinno, A. (2020). A visual tool for supporting decision-making in privacy oriented software development. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces* (5 pp.). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3399715.3399818>
- Barriage, S., & Hicks, A. (2020). Mobile apps for visual research: Affordances and challenges for participant-generated photography. *Library & Information Science Research*, 42(3), 101033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2020.101033>
- Brandt, J., Weiss, N., & Klemmer, S. R. (2007). txt 4 18r: Lowering the burden for diary studies under mobile conditions. In *CHI '07 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 2303–2308). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1240866.1240998>
- Davidson, J. C., Karadzhov, D., & Wilson, G. (2024). Short Take: Designing a Multinational Smartphone App Survey during COVID-19: Rewards, Risks, and Recommendations. *Field Methods*, 0(0), 15 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X231218192>

- Do, J., & Yamagata-Lynch, L. C. (2017). Designing and developing cell phone applications for qualitative research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 23(10), 757–767. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800417731085>
- Felderer, M., Goedicke, M., Grunse, L., Hasselbring, W., Lamprecht, A.-L., & Rumpe, B. (2023). Toward research software engineering research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8020525>
- Frąckowiak, M., Rogowski, Ł., & Sommer, V. (2023). Hopes and challenges of creating and using a smartphone application. Working on and working with a digital mobile tool in qualitative sociospatial research. *Qualitative Research*, 23(5), 1378–1397. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14687941221098923>
- Fung, C., Motti, V., Zhang, K., & Qian, Y. (2022). A Study of User Concerns about Smartphone Privacy. In *2022 6th Cyber Security in Networking Conference (CSNet)* (8 pp.). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNet56116.2022.9955623>
- GDPR (2016): Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), Pub. L. No. Regulation (EU) 2016/679. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>
- Glass, R. L. (2003). Error-free software remains extremely elusive. *IEEE Software*, 20(1), 104–103. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2003.1159042>
- Hektner, J. M., Schmidt, J. A., & Csikszentmihályi, M. (2007). *Experience Sampling Method. Measuring the quality of everyday life*. SAGE.
- Johnson, A. (2013). Exploring the use of mobile technology in qualitative inquiry in africa. *The Qualitative Report*, 18(22). https://rdw.rowan.edu/education_facpub/1
- Kaufmann, K., & Peil, C. (2020). The mobile instant messaging interview (MIMI): Using WhatsApp to enhance self-reporting and explore media usage in situ. *Mobile Media & Communication*, 8(2), 229–246. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050157919852392>
- Keusch, F., Struminskaya, B., Antoun, C., Couper, M. P., & Kreuter, F. (2019). Willingness to participate in passive mobile data collection. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 83(S1), 210–235. <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfz007>
- Khan, M. N. A., Mirza, A. M., Wagan, R. A., Shahid, M., & Saleem, I. (2020). A Literature Review on Software Testing Techniques for Smartphone Applications. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 10(6), 6578–6583. <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3844>
- Kümpel, A. S. (2022). Using messaging apps in audience research: An approach to study everyday information and news use practices. *Digital Journalism*, 10(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2020.1864219>

- Lathia, N. (2012). Using idle moments to record your health via mobile applications. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM Workshop on Mobile Systems for Computational Social Science* (pp. 22–27). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2307863.2307871>
- Lobur, M., Shcherbovskykh, S., & Stefanovych, T. (2020). Availability audit of IoT system data reserved by 3-2-1 backup strategy based on fault tree and state transition diagram analysis. In *2020 IEEE 15th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (pp. 343–346). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSIT49958.2020.9321992>
- Maseeh, H. I., Nahar, S., Jebarajakirthy, C., Ross, M., Arli, D., Das, M., Rehman, M., & Ashraf, H. A. (2023). Exploring the privacy concerns of smartphone app users: A qualitative approach. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 41(7), 945–969. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-11-2022-0515>
- Menendez, H. D. (2021). Software testing or the bugs' nightmare. *Open Journal of Software Engineering*, (21 pp.). <https://doi.org/10.46723/ojse.1.1.1>
- Merino, L., Ghafari, M., & Nierstrasz, O. (2018). Towards actionable visualization for software developers. *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*, 30(2), e1923. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.1923>
- Papathanasaki, M., Maglaras, L., & Ayres, N. (2022). Modern authentication methods: A comprehensive survey. *AI, Computer Science and Robotics Technology*, (24 pp.). <https://doi.org/10.5772/acrt.08>
- Roberts, C., Herzing, J. M. E., Manjon, M. A., Abbet, P., & Gatica-Perez, D. (2022). Response burden and dropout in a probability-based online panel study – A comparison between an app and browser-based design. *Journal of Official Statistics*, 38(4), 987–1017. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jos-2022-0043>
- Seifert, A., Hofer, M., & Allemand, M. (2018). Mobile data collection: Smart, but not (yet) smart enough. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 12. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnins.2018.00971>
- Siegler, A. J., Knox, J., Bauermeister, J. A., Golinkoff, J., Hightow-Weidman, L., & Scott, H. (2021). Mobile app development in health research: pitfalls and solutions. *mHealth*, 7(32). <https://doi.org/10.21037/mhealth-19-263>
- Snedaker, S., & Rima, C. (2014). *Business continuity and disaster recovery planning for IT professionals*. Waltham: Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2012-0-06206-0>
- StatCounter. (2024a). Android – Anteile der Versionen November 2023 (2024, Jan. 02). <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/180113/umfrage/anteil-der-verschiedenen-android-versionen-auf-geraeten-mit-android-os/>
- StatCounter. (2024b). Mobile Betriebssysteme – Marktanteile Internetnutzung weltweit bis November 2023 (2024, Jan. 02). <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/184335/umfrage/marktanteil-der-mobilen-betriebssysteme-weltweit-seit-2009/>

- Sung, W. (2016). A study of the digital divide in the current phase of the information age: The moderating effect of smartphones. *Information Polity*, 21(3), 291–306. <https://doi.org/10.3233/IP-160398>
- Tamrin, S. I., Norman, A. A., & Hamid, S. (2017). Information systems security practices in social software applications: A systematic literature review. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 69(2), 131–157. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-08-2016-0124>
- Velásquez, I., Caro, A., & Rodríguez, A. (2018). Authentication schemes and methods: A systematic literature review. *Information and Software Technology*, 94 (Febr.), 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2017.09.012>
- Vicente-Saez, R., & Martinez-Fuentes, C. (2018). Open science now: A systematic literature review for an integrated definition. *Journal of Business Research*, 88 (July), 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.043>
- Welford, J., Sandhu, J., Collinson, B., & Blatchford, S. (2022). Collecting qualitative data using a smartphone app: Learning from research involving people with experience of multiple disadvantage. *Methodological Innovations*, 15(3), 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20597991221114570>
- Wenz, A., & Keusch, F. (2023). Increasing the Acceptance of Smartphone-Based Data Collection. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 87(2), 357–388. <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfad019>

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